

1 Protocol: Testing the performance of INVITES-IN, a tool for 2 assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies

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44 Disclaimers

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52 Abstract

53 A tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies called INVITES-IN is currently under
54 development. The tool is designed specifically for cell culture studies.

55 This protocol describes the testing of the performance of INVITES-IN. By performance, we
56 mean the extent to which results of using INVITES-IN are the same for different users
57 (consistency), the amount of time and cognitive effort it takes to apply INVITES-IN (assessor
58 workload), the precision and potential for systematic error in results of applying INVITES-IN
59 (accuracy), and how easy it is to use INVITES-IN (user experience).

60 The participants in the user testing will be representative for the expected end-users of
61 INVITES-IN which are persons preparing literature reviews including *in vitro* studies (e.g. in
62 the context of chemical hazard and risk assessments or drug development). All end-users
63 are expected to have experience with *in vitro* methods.

64 Data collected from the performance testing will be used for further refinement and
65 development of the release version of INVITES-IN.

66 Key words

67 Cell culture, evidence-based toxicology, risk of bias, user testing.

68 1. Introduction

69 We are developing a tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies called INVITES-
70 IN (detailed description of the creation of this tool is available in the protocol by Svendsen et
71 al. (2023)). INVITES-IN will be designed specifically to be applied to eukaryotic cell culture
72 studies including cell lines, primary cells, co-cultures, monolayer and 3-D cell systems. As
73 we are not able to directly measure internal validity, INVITES-IN will be designed to address
74 the risk for introduction of different types of bias (risk of bias; RoB) to the cell culture studies.
75 In this protocol, we describe how we will test the performance of INVITES-IN. The
76 participants in the user testing will be representative for the expected end-users of INVITES-
77 IN which are persons preparing literature reviews including *in vitro* studies e.g. in the context
78 of chemical hazard and risk assessments or drug development. This includes persons
79 having practical experience from carrying out *in vitro* studies, and/or experience with
80 evaluating evidence from *in vitro* studies.

81 INVITES-IN will consist of two elements: a set of signalling questions addressing different
82 sources of bias (e.g. selection bias, performance bias, detection bias) that may be of
83 importance for the internal validity of the study, and a guidance document containing step-
84 by-step instructions explaining how to assess the degree of bias through the rating of the
85 signalling questions. The outcome of the three studies described in the protocol for the
86 creation of INVITES-IN (Svendsen et al., 2023) will determine which bias domains and items
87 that will be included in INVITES-IN. The users of INVITES-IN will answer the signalling
88 questions in order to determine whether bias might have been introduced. For each
89 signalling question, the criteria that will be used for assessing the risk for introduction of bias
90 will be described in the guidance document. A signalling question is judged as being low risk
91 for introduction of bias when all criteria for that question are fulfilled.

92 The creation of INVITES-IN follows the framework of general principles for developing
93 quality assessment tools as suggested by Whiting et al. (2017). Four studies will be

94 performed to develop, test, refine and issue the release version of the tool. The first three
95 studies are described in Svendsen et al. 2023. In the first study, the relevance of bias
96 domains and items for *in vitro* studies were interpreted through focus group discussions. In
97 the second study, the importance and impact of the relevant bias items for *in vitro* studies
98 will be evaluated and ranked using a modified Delphi method. In the third study, the beta
99 version of INVITES-IN will be created, based on the outcome of the first two studies. With
100 the fourth study, the performance testing, we aim to identify how well the tool works in
101 practice to identify needs for improvement that should be considered when creating the
102 release version of INVITES-IN. The current protocol describes the fourth study.

103 1.1 Objective

104 The objective of this study is to test the performance of INVITES-IN as a tool for assessing
105 internal validity of cell culture studies to collect information for further refinement and
106 development of the release version of INVITES-IN. The following will be evaluated:

- 107 1. Consistency, in terms of the extent to which results of using INVITES-IN are the same for
108 different users.
- 109 2. Assessor workload, in terms of the amount of time and cognitive effort it takes to apply
110 INVITES-IN.
- 111 3. Accuracy in the application of INVITES-IN to evaluate cell culture studies, in terms of the
112 precision against the gold-standard application and potential for systematic error in
113 results.
- 114 4. User experience in applying the tool, in terms of how easy it is to use INVITES-IN.

115 Testing the generalisability of INVITES-IN, i.e., how well the tool performs for assessment of
116 the internal validity of other studies than cell culture studies, does not fall under the scope of
117 this study.

118 1.2 Project governance

119 The development of INVITES-IN is part of the project "[Next Generation Risk Assessment in
120 Practice](#)" (VKM, 2023). This project is led by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health
121 represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment, and the
122 partners involved in this project are the Benaki Phytopathological Institute, the Italian
123 Institute of Health, and the University of Basel. The project is part of the European
124 Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals ([PARC](#)) [Project 101057014].
125 PARC aims to develop next generation chemical risk assessment to advance research,
126 share knowledge and improve skills, protecting human health and the environment. The

127 present project is included in the PARC task focusing on facilitation of regulatory acceptance
128 and use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs).

129 A project group (PG) has been established with the responsibility for drafting the protocol
130 and performing the study.

131 A scientific advisory group (SAG) consisting of experts in methods for tool development,
132 systematic review methods, chemical risk assessment methods, toxicology, and/or NAMs
133 has been established to share information about ongoing projects addressing similar
134 questions to ensure that the outcome of this project complements the work of others and
135 thereby creates synergies and avoids duplication of efforts, and to give strategic guidance
136 and support.

137 2 Methods

138 2.1 General methodological issues

139 The performance testing consists of two exercises: the user testing, in which the application
140 of INVITES-IN is evaluated in an emulated systematic review; and the creation of a “gold-
141 standard” application of INVITES-IN, to which the results of the user testing can be
142 compared. The gold-standard is a reference application of INVITES-IN. Cell culture studies
143 having different degrees of bias will be identified through the process of the generation of the
144 gold-standard and included in the practical exercise. This is important to ensure that the
145 whole guidance document will be applied by the participants in the practical exercise. In
146 addition, this should allow to interpret to what degree INVITES-IN succeeds to differentiate
147 studies with a higher internal validity from studies with a lower internal validity.

148 2.1.1 Structure of the performance evaluation

149 An overview of the structure of the performance test of INVITES-IN is shown in Figure 1.

150

151 **Figure 1.** The structure of the performance testing.

152 The creation of the gold-standard is described in Section 2.2.1. The user testing (Section
 153 2.2.2) consists of a practical exercise (Section 2.2.2.2) and a survey (Section 2.2.2.3). The
 154 data collected will be used to assess consistency, assessor workload, accuracy, and user
 155 experience as shown in Figure 2.

156

157 **Figure 2.** An overview of the performance testing.

158 An overview of the tasks and responsibilities of the project group (PG) and the SAG in the
 159 planning and execution of the user test and the creation of the gold-standard is given in
 160 Table 1.

161 **Table 1.** Tasks and responsibilities in the testing of INVITES-IN.

Phase	Task	Responsible
Planning	Define inclusion criteria for participants.	Project group and scientific advisory group
	Nominate and recruit participants fulfilling the inclusion criteria.	

	Prepare the request for participant information.	Project group
	Select cell culture studies for the practical exercise and create the gold-standard.	
	Prepare the survey.	
Execution	The collection of participant information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants complete the questionnaire. 	Project group
	The practical exercise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pairs of testers are established. • Participants receive a cell culture study for training. • Training sessions are arranged. • Participants receive the cell culture studies. • Participants individually rate the cell culture studies. • Pair of participants (judge pairs) meet to compare, discuss, and reconcile their ratings. 	
	The survey <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants complete the survey. 	
	Data analyses	

162 An overview of the estimated workload for the participants is given in Figure 3. Participants
163 not responding within the allocated deadline for completing the practical exercise will be
164 excluded. Removed participants will not be replaced, unless it is necessary to reach the
165 desired number of participants.

166
167 **Figure 3.** Estimated workload for the participants. *The number of cell culture studies each
168 participant will receive depends on the total number of participants recruited (see Section
169 2.3.1).

170 2.1.2 Ethical approval

171 Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian
172 Institute of Public Health on February 7th, 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is
173 not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.

174 2.2 Data collection

175 2.2.1 Selection of cell culture studies and creation of the gold-standard

176 The gold-standard will be created by a group of four to five PG members. All members in this
177 group participate in the creation of gold-standard evaluations for each cell culture study
178 included in the practical exercise. To harmonise the ratings given by the members in the
179 group, all members start by evaluating the same three studies and then meet to compare
180 and discuss the ratings. The members will then evaluate the same five studies and meet to
181 discuss and compare the ratings, and so on. Consensus in the group will be required for
182 completion of the gold-standards. The gold-standard will be created during the process of
183 identification of cell culture studies for the practical exercise as illustrated in Figure 4 (Step
184 5).

185 The procedure for identification of cell culture studies for the practical exercise and the
186 creation of a gold-standard for each study includes seven steps (Figure 4). Systematic
187 reviews including cell culture studies were identified in a literature search (step 1 in Figure
188 4). The eligibility criteria used for the selection of the systematic reviews were as follows:

- 189 a) A literature search was performed.
- 190 b) The PECO (population, exposure, comparator, outcome)/ PEO (population, exposure,
191 outcome) statement is clear.
- 192 c) Quality or RoB of the included studies have been assessed.
- 193 d) At least one of the included cell culture studies is categorised as high quality/ low RoB
194 and at least one is categorised as low quality/ high RoB.

195 Criteria c) and d) were included in attempt to identify cell culture studies of varying risk of
196 bias and varying quality, as all should be included in the user testing.

197 The literature search and study selection are described in Supplementary materials 1, and
198 includes search terms, search strategy, and study selection (Figure S1 (flow chart), Table S1
199 (included systematic reviews), and Table S2 (excluded publications, with reason)). An
200 overview of the publications in the included systematic reviews that are categorised as high
201 quality/ low RoB or low quality/ high RoB is given in Table S3 (step 2 in Figure 4). An

202 overview of all cell culture studies included in these publications will be created (step 3 in
203 Figure 4) and will be the starting point for the random selection of cell culture studies for the
204 practical exercise (step 4 in Figure 4). The PG members developing INVITES-IN will create
205 the gold-standard for these studies by rating all signalling question for each study according
206 to the beta version of INVITES-IN (step 5 in Figure 4). The gold-standards should include
207 more than one rating option for each signalling question (step 6 in Figure 4). If this is not
208 achieved, steps 4 and 5 (Figure 4) will be repeated until this is fulfilled (step 7 in Figure 4).
209 When this is fulfilled, these cell culture studies will constitute the pool of cell culture studies
210 for the practical exercise.

211

212 **Figure 4.** The seven steps to create the pool of cell culture studies for the practical exercise
213 and the gold-standard for each study.

214 The number of cell culture studies needed for the practical exercise depends on the number
215 of user testing participants and this is addressed in Section 2.3.1.

216 2.2.2 User Testing

217 2.2.2.1 Participant selection and enrolment

218 The participants in the user testing will be scientists having good working knowledge with *in*
219 *vitro* methods, with or without systematic review and chemical risk assessment expertise,
220 affiliated in academic institutions, governmental institutions (including risk assessment
221 institutions and research institutes), and private sector research institutions (eligibility criteria
222 are presented in Table 2).

223 The participants should be able to work in pairs during parts of the practical exercise (see
224 Section 2.2.2.2). Participant information including affiliation, years of experience with *in vitro*
225 studies, years of experience with chemical risk assessment, and years of experience with
226 systematic reviews will be collected using a questionnaire (see Supplementary materials 3).

227 No financial compensation or other incentives are offered for the participation; however, the
228 participants will be eligible to be co-authors of the user testing study manuscript if they also
229 read and comment on the final draft.

230 **Table 2.** Eligibility criteria for participation in the user testing study.

Scientific experience or expertise	<i>In vitro</i> methods OR <i>In vitro</i> methods AND systematic review methods OR <i>In vitro</i> methods AND chemical risk assessment
Academic level	PhD degree completed
Language	English, level B1 or higher
Affiliation	Academia
	Governmental institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes)
	Private sector research institutions
	NGOs
	Self-employed or freelancer researchers

231 *2.2.2.2 The practical exercise*

232 The practical exercise aims to emulate a real-world application of INVITES-IN by simulating
233 the validity assessment step in the systematic review process, albeit in a controlled
234 environment. The validity assessment step includes critical appraisal of studies by pair of
235 experts that first do the assessment individually and then harmonise the results.

236 Before the practical exercise is started, participants will receive one cell culture study for
237 self-train on the application of INVITES-IN, and training sessions will be arranged to clarify
238 initial questions and uncertainties. An overview of the most frequently asked questions will
239 be created and made available for all participants.

240 If a publication contains several cell culture studies/experiments, a participant will only be
241 asked to evaluate one of these. Participants will receive the publication and the selected cell
242 culture experiment will be highlighted to ensure that INVITES-IN will be applied to the correct
243 experiment.

244 To emulate the systematic review process, all cell culture studies included in the practical
245 exercise will be tagged with a research question formulated based on the extracted
246 PECO/PEO from the systematic review in which it was found (see 2.2.1 and Supplementary
247 materials 1). Each study will first be evaluated individually by a participant, followed by a
248 calibration in pairs. The pairs will always be the same. When the practical exercise is started,
249 the two participants in a pair will receive the same cell culture studies in a given order (the
250 allocated studies for a pair will be numbered as study one, study two, etc.). Participants
251 receive study one first and will not receive study two before they have sent the evaluation of
252 study one to the PG. This way we ensure that the studies are evaluated in a given order.

253 Participants will be requested to time themselves, and to report the time used for the rating
254 of each study in the survey they will receive when the practical exercise is completed (see
255 Section 2.2.2.3). The process for the practical exercise is illustrated in Figure 5.

256

257 **Figure 5.** An overview of the practical exercise.

258

259 **2.2.2.3 The survey**

260 In the survey, consisting of three parts, participants will give feedback based on their
 261 experience using the beta version of INVITES-IN to evaluate internal validity (see
 262 Supplementary materials 2).

263 In the first part, participants rate agreement with statements on the cognitive burden and
 264 intuitiveness of applying the tool. For each statement, participants may provide more details
 265 as free text. In the second part, participants are asked to time themselves when rating each
 266 cell culture study (cell culture study 1, cell culture study 2, etc.). They will also be asked how
 267 confident they are that they timed themselves accurately, and given the options “very
 268 confident”, “somewhat confident”, “somewhat unsure”, or “very unsure”. In the third part,
 269 participants are requested to answer questions related to user experience,

270 **2.3 Data analysis and reporting**

271 All analyses will be done by the PG members.

272 All raw data will be anonymised and made available as supplementary to the user test
 273 report. The number of participants completing the practical exercise will be reported. All
 274 ratings of signalling questions, both pre- and post-reconciliation ratings, will be presented

275 and made available. The number of participants completing the survey will be reported. All
276 feedback on user experience will be made available.

277 Regarding participant information, participant response (in percentage), gender distribution
278 (in percent), and experience with *in vitro* methods, chemical risk assessment and systematic
279 review methods, will be reported.

280 2.3.1 Assessing consistency

281 Consistency in assessing internal validity using INVITES-IN, in terms of the extent to which
282 results of the application of the tool are the same for different users, will be measured as
283 inter-rater reliability using the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) of the studies. Low
284 consistency may be due to varying level and specific field of expertise and/or insufficient or
285 imprecise information in the guidance. The ICC calculations will be used to identify needs for
286 improvement of the guidance. Data on participant expertise will be collected (see
287 Supplementary materials 3) and used to see if there are correlations between the level of
288 consistency and the level and type of expertise. However, statistical analyses addressing
289 such effects will not be performed as we are not able to power the study for such analyses.

290 We will measure inter-rater reliability for the post-reconciliation ratings from the practical
291 exercise (one rating per judge pair per cell culture study), and it will be measured per
292 signalling question for all studies. The ratings for each signalling question will be ordinal, and
293 the studies will be distributed in a weaved manner to counteract the bias from a learning.
294 The assessment of consistency is described in detail in Section 2.3.1.1, and sample size
295 estimation is described in detail in Section 2.3.1.2.

296 2.3.1.1 Detailed description of the statistical methods

297 The ratings for each signalling question will be ordinal with three, four, or five levels ($Y = 1,$
298 $2, 3, Y = 1, 2, 3, 4,$ or $Y = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$; the number of rating options will be decided during the
299 creation of INVITES-IN). The ICC for each signalling question will be calculated for each
300 signalling question via a mixed-effects linear regression model:

$$301 \quad Y_{jk} = \mu + \alpha_j + \beta_k + \epsilon_{jk}$$

302 where Y_{jk} is the rating corresponding to study j that was rated by judge pair k . μ is the overall
303 mean rating, α_j represents the study effect, β_k represents the judge pair effect, and
304 ϵ_{jk} represents unexplained variation/random error effect.

305 The ICC (correlation of two observations of the same study) is then calculated by:

306
$$ICC = \frac{\sigma_{\alpha}^2}{\sigma_{\alpha}^2 + \sigma_{\beta}^2 + \sigma_{\epsilon}^2}$$

307 where σ_{α}^2 is the variance of α (study effect), σ_{β}^2 is the variance of β (judge pair effect), and σ_{ϵ}^2
 308 is the variance of ϵ (unexplained variation/random error). The total variation of the outcome
 309 (Y) can be expressed as $\sigma_{\alpha}^2 + \sigma_{\beta}^2 + \sigma_{\epsilon}^2$.

310 95% confidence intervals for the ICC are then obtained by performing model-based semi-
 311 parametric bootstrapping, using the `lme4::bootMer` function in R, and taking the 2.5th and
 312 97.5th percentiles.

313 The ICC of the studies can be interpreted as the amount of variation (of the outcome)
 314 attributable to differences between the studies. The ICC value ranges from 0 to 1, with
 315 higher values indicating greater consistency of agreement between the ratings of a signalling
 316 question. That is, if the ICC of the studies is 0.6, the appropriate interpretation is that 60% of
 317 the total variance in the ratings is due to differences between the studies, and 40% of the
 318 total variance in the ratings is due to other causes (i.e., judge pair effect and random error).

319 The studies will be distributed in a weaved manner to counteract the bias from a learning
 320 effect as illustrated in Table 3. The resultant ICC can be interpreted roughly as the ICC after
 321 3 attempts, as it is a blended ICC with equal number of studies rated in attempt 1, 2, 3, 4,
 322 and 5.

323 **Table 3.** Illustrating the distribution of studies to the judge pairs. A red **P** demarcates a
 324 practice study, which will not be included in the final analysis. X1 demarcates the first study
 325 and the judge pair’s first attempt to apply INVITES-IN, X2 demarcates the second study and
 326 the judge pair’s second attempt to apply INVITES-IN, etc.

Study	Judge pair (40 participants = 20 judge pairs)																			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2
2	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3
3	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4
4	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5
5	X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P				
6		X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P			
7			X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P		
8				X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P	
9					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P

10	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1	P					X5	X4	X3	X2	X1
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327

328 *2.3.1.2 Sample size estimation*

329 The number of studies that will be rated by a pair depends on the number of participants that
330 we manage to recruit (Tables 4, 5, and 6). Sample size estimates were made through
331 simulations.

332 The simulation process for four possible ratings of each signalling question (Y=1, 2, 3, 4;
333 Table 5) is described in detail. The scenarios where the possible ratings of each signalling
334 question are three (Y=1, 2, 3; Table 4) or five (Y=1, 2, 3, 4, 5; Table 6) were simulated in a
335 similar manner and hence do not need to be described. 100 000 fictional studies were
336 simulated, of which 25 000 corresponded to $Y^{true} = 1$, 25 000 corresponded to $Y^{true} = 2$,
337 and so on.

338 From here, multiple scenarios were considered, where the number of judge pairs and the
339 number of studies reviewed per judge pair were altered. For each scenario, the 100 000
340 studies (or less, as appropriate) were assigned to 10 000 judge pairs. A new outcome (Y)
341 was created to provide an ICC of approximately 0.65. For 78.5% of the judge pair/paper
342 combinations, Y was equal to Y^{true} (i.e. the judge pair accurately assessed the paper). To
343 create disagreements between the judges, for 21.5% of the judge pair/paper combinations, a
344 number was randomly selected between 1 and 4 (R code provided in supplemental materials
345 4).

346
$$\Pr(Y_{jk} = Y_{jk}^{true}) = 0.785$$

347
$$\Pr(Y_{jk} = random(1,2,3,4)) = 0.215$$

348 Where Y_{jk} is the rating corresponding to study j that was rated by judge pair k , as previously
349 noted in section 2.3.1.1.

350 The ICC estimation was then performed multiple times (e.g., if the scenario needed 10 judge
351 pairs, then the ICC estimation was performed 1000 times) as explained in section 2.3.1.1.

352 For each of the ICC estimations, the margin of error (MOE) was calculated (MOE = half the
353 width of the bootstrapped 95% confidence interval). The mean MOE of each scenario is
354 presented in Tables 4-6. The mean MOE was chosen to be presented as it represents how
355 reliable our estimates are (R code provided in Supplemental materials 4).

356 A maximum MOE of 0.15 was considered to be acceptable. According to Koo and Li (2016),
 357 ICC values less than 0.5 are indicative of poor inter-rater reliability for a signalling question,
 358 whereas ICC values between 0.5 and 0.75, between 0.75 and 0.9, and greater than 0.90 are
 359 indicative of moderate, good, and excellent reliability, respectively. By estimating the MOE
 360 when the true ICC is 0.65 and setting the acceptable MOE to 0.15, we will be able to
 361 differentiate between poorer (ICC less than 0.5) and better (ICC \leq 0.5) inter-rater reliability.

362 **Table 4.** Sample size estimates for the number of cell culture studies needed to be assessed
 363 by the judge pairs to have a $MOE \leq 0.15$ given three rating options of a signalling question
 364 (Y=1, 2, 3).

95% margin of error for estimating ICC when the true ICC is 0.65, for Y=1, 2, 3						
Judge pairs	Number of cell culture studies reviewed per judge pair					
	5	6	7	8	9	10
10	0.23	0.21	0.20	0.18	0.18	0.17
12	0.21	0.20	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.16
14	0.20	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14
16	0.19	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.15	0.14
18	0.18	0.16	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.13
20	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.12
22	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12
24	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12
26	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.11
28	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.11	0.10
30	0.14	0.13	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.10

365 Abbreviations: ICC, Intraclass Correlation Coefficient; MOE; margin of error; Y, rating option.

366

367 **Table 5.** Sample size estimates for the number of cell culture studies needed to be assessed
 368 by the judge pairs to have a $MOE \leq 0.15$ given four rating options of a signalling question
 369 (Y=1, 2, 3, 4).

95% margin of error for estimating ICC when the true ICC is 0.65, for Y=1, 2, 3, 4						
Judge pairs	Number of cell culture studies reviewed per judge pair					
	5	6	7	8	9	10
10	0.23	0.23	0.21	0.20	0.19	0.17
12	0.21	0.21	0.20	0.18	0.17	0.15

14	0.21	0.19	0.19	0.18	0.17	0.15
16	0.19	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14
18	0.18	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.13
20	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12
22	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12
24	0.16	0.15	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.11
26	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.11
28	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.10
30	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.12	0.11	0.10

370 Abbreviations: ICC, Intraclass Correlation Coefficient; MOE; margin of error; Y, rating option.

371

372 **Table 6.** Sample size estimates for the number of cell culture studies needed to be assessed
373 by the judge pairs to have a $MOE \leq 0.15$ given five rating options of a signalling question
374 (Y=1, 2, 3, 4, 5).

95% margin of error for estimating ICC when the true ICC is 0.5, for Y=1, 2, 3, 4, 5						
Judge pairs	Number of cell culture studies reviewed per judge pair					
	5	6	7	8	9	10
10	0.23	0.23	0.19	0.19	0.16	0.17
12	0.21	0.21	0.17	0.18	0.15	0.15
14	0.20	0.20	0.17	0.16	0.14	0.15
16	0.18	0.18	0.15	0.15	0.13	0.13
18	0.18	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.12	0.13
20	0.17	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.12
22	0.16	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.11	0.12
24	0.16	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.11
26	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.11
28	0.14	0.14	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.11
30	0.14	0.13	0.11	0.12	0.10	0.10

375 Abbreviations: ICC, Intraclass Correlation Coefficient; MOE; margin of error; Y, rating option.

376 2.3.2 Assessing assessor workload

377 Assessor workload in applying INVITES-IN will be assessed as the amount of time it takes to
378 apply the tool, and the cognitive burden or intuitiveness of applying the tool. The participants
379 will be instructed to time all time spent on the evaluation, which includes reading the study,

380 identifying the necessary information, conducting additional information gathering (when
381 necessary) and answering and giving reasoning for all the signalling questions.

382 Median and mean time to complete the assessments of one cell culture study (part 2 of the
383 survey) will be reported. Subgroup analyses may be performed to evaluate the effect of
384 having systematic review experience.

385 All data on the cognitive burden or intuitiveness (part 1 of the survey) of applying the tool will
386 be reported.

387 2.3.3 Assessing accuracy

388 Accuracy of the tool, in terms of precision of the results of application of INVITES-IN and the
389 potential for systematic differences between the results of typical user evaluations of a study
390 and the gold-standard reference evaluation, will be measured by comparing the post-
391 reconciliation ratings and the gold-standard. How precisely INVITES-IN characterises
392 internal validity will be measured as the association between the ratings of participants and
393 the gold-standard for the same signalling question for the same study and by identification of
394 learning effects (Section 2.3.3.1). The potential for systematic differences will be described
395 via histograms of the user-ratings for each level of the gold-standard ratings (Section
396 2.3.3.2).

397 2.3.3.1 Precision

398 To see if there is an association between the gold-standard reference rating and the judge
399 pair ratings, a matrix of ratings will be formed with the gold-standard forming one axis and
400 the post-reconciliation ratings forming the other axis. From this matrix, two analyses will be
401 performed. Firstly, Fisher's exact test will be performed to assess if there is evidence that the
402 user-ratings are statistically associated with the gold-standard ratings. Results indicating no
403 difference between the gold-standard and the user-ratings are shown in Table 7.

404 **Table 7.** For all data from the practical exercise; illustrating results indicating no difference
405 between the gold-standard and user-ratings. Comparison of the gold-standard with ratings
406 from 40 study assessments, where the ratings are equally divided for the different rating
407 options (Y=1, 2, 3 or 4). The gold-standard rating is indicated in the table with grey colouring
408 of table cells. This analysis will be repeated for all signalling questions.

	Gold-standard rating
--	----------------------

All data (SQ=1)		Y=1	Y=2	Y=3	Y=4
Judge pair ratings	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=1	10	0	0	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=2	0	10	0	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=3	0	0	10	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=4	0	0	0	10

409 Abbreviations: SQ, signalling question; Y, rating option.

410

411 The secondary analysis will be primarily used to attempt to identify if there is a learning
412 effect. The aforementioned analyses (Table 7) will be repeated five times, with data
413 restricted to the judge pair's first attempt to apply INVITES-IN to evaluate the internal validity
414 of a cell culture study, second attempt, third attempt, fourth attempt, and fifth attempt,
415 meaning that a study will be assessed five times. Furthermore, matrix of ratings will be
416 constructed where the data is restricted to gold-standard Y=1, Y=2, Y=3, Y=4, one axis
417 corresponds to first attempt, second attempt, third attempt, fourth attempt, and the fifth
418 attempt to apply INVITES-IN to a cell culture study, and the other axis corresponds to the
419 post-reconciliation ratings (Y=1, 2, 3, 4) (Tables 8, 9, and 10). Results indicating a small
420 difference between gold-standard and user-ratings, no difference between gold-standard
421 and user-ratings, and a learning effect are shown in Tables 8, 9, and 10, respectively.

422 **Table 8.** Data restricted to the first attempt to apply INVITES-IN to a cell culture study;
423 results indicating small difference between gold-standard and user-ratings. Comparison of
424 the gold-standard with ratings from 40 study assessments, where the rating options are Y=1,
425 2, 3 or 4. The gold-standard rating is indicated in the table with grey colouring of table cells.
426 This analysis will be repeated for all signalling questions.

	Gold-standard rating
--	----------------------

Restrict data to first attempt (SQ=1)		Y=1	Y=2	Y=3	Y=4
Judge pair ratings	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=1	7	1	1	1
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=2	1	7	1	1
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=3	1	1	7	1
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=4	1	1	1	7

427 Abbreviations: SQ, signalling question; Y, rating option.

428

429 **Table 9.** Data restricted to the second attempt to apply INVITES-IN to a cell culture study;
430 results indicating no difference between gold-standard and user-ratings. Comparison of the
431 gold-standard with ratings from 40 study assessments, where the rating options are Y=1, 2,
432 3 or 4. The gold-standard rating is indicated in the table with grey colouring of table cells.
433 This analysis will be repeated for all signalling questions.

Restrict data to second attempt (SQ=1)		Gold-standard rating			
		Y=1	Y=2	Y=3	Y=4
Judge pair ratings	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=1	10	0	0	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=2	0	10	0	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=3	0	0	10	0
	Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=4	0	0	0	10

434 Abbreviations: SQ, signalling question; Y, rating option.

435

436 **Table 10.** Results indicating a learning effect, assuming 40 judge pairs rating one signalling
437 question for 40 studies with a gold-standard rating Y=1. The rating options are Y=1, 2, 3 or
438 4. The data is restricted to when the gold-standard rating is Y=1. This analysis will be
439 repeated for all signalling questions, and for Y=1, 2, 3 and 4.

Restrict data to gold-standard Y=1 (SQ=1)	Attempt 1	Attempt 2	Attempt 3	Attempt 4	Attempt 5
Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=1	10	20	25	30	35
Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=2	10	10	15	10	5
Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=3	10	10	0	0	0
Number of judge pairs selecting the rating option Y=4	10	0	0	0	0

440 Abbreviations: SQ, signalling question; Y, rating option.

441 [2.3.3.2 Bias](#)

442 The potential for systematic difference between user-ratings and the gold-standard will be
443 described via histograms of the user-ratings for each level of the gold-standard ratings due
444 to the small number of categories in the outcome (i.e., one histogram of user-ratings when
445 gold-standard rating = 1, another histogram of user-ratings when gold-standard rating = 2,
446 ...). If the Fisher's exact test (Section 2.3.3.1) is statistically significant, then these
447 histograms (along with additional summary statistics, such as the mean/median, or
448 cumulative distribution function) will be interpreted to identify if the user-ratings are positively
449 associated with the gold-standard reference ratings.

450 [2.3.4 Reporting qualitative data on user experience](#)

451 The user experience in applying the tool (Part 3 of the survey), in terms of qualitative
452 feedback about the process of applying INVITES-IN, will constitute of free text answers to

453 questions. Overviews of all answers to each question will be prepared and made available. If
454 possible, we will identify trends in the answers to each question, and the answers will then
455 be grouped according to these trends. Overviews of the rating of each question will be
456 prepared and made available.

457 3 Results and creation of the release version of INVITES-IN

458 All results from the data analyses will be used to evaluate the performance of INVITES-IN as
459 a tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies. Creating the release version of
460 INVITES-IN, these results will be the basis for all discussions regarding needs for
461 adjustments of the INVITES-IN version that was applied for the user testing.

462 Results from the practical exercise, such as if data on reasoning for the rating of a signalling
463 question clearly shows that several of the test users have interpreted the guidance
464 incorrectly or differently, will be used to identify needs for improvement of the guidance
465 together with the feedback from the survey. In addition, poor inter-rater reliability will be
466 interpreted as needs for improvement/revision such as clarification of the guidance.

467 The structure of INVITES-IN, layout, and other presentational or user-experience related
468 characteristics can be adjusted in response to the outcome of user testing, e.g. in response
469 to feedback on the survey questions addressing how the tool, and the usability of the tool,
470 can be improved.

471 The signalling questions will not be revised, unless in the judgement of the PG, informed by
472 the SAG, there are sufficient grounds for changing a signalling question, and there is good
473 reason for believing the change made will improve INVITES-IN. This may be done in
474 response to feedback on the survey question addressing which signalling questions the
475 users found most challenging to answer, and why this question was particularly challenging.

476 The PG and SAG will decide on which improvements should be performed to the guidance
477 and the structure/layout, and justification for the decisions will be included in the user testing
478 report. PG members involved in this study will make the final decisions on improvements
479 and prepare the release version.

480 4. Limitations

481 By recruiting from the network of PG and SAG members, we attempt to involve a broad and
482 diverse group of experts from different institutions in the user testing, while working within
483 the resources that the research team has available. However, the final group of participants
484 may not be representative of all potential users of the tool.”

485 The study is not powered to allow meaningful analysis of impact of participant characteristics
486 on the results. It was considered not possible to power the study for such analyses because
487 the number of participants needed would be higher than can be achieved with the resources
488 available to the research team.

489 The study is not powered to allow analysis of impact of *in vitro* studies on the results. It was
490 considered not possible to power the study for such analyses because the number of studies
491 that would need analysing is unrealistically high.

492 Dissemination

493 A report describing the user testing study, including all results, will be published.

494 The final version of INVITES-IN will be published as peer-review journal article and
495 disseminated through PG and SAG members.

496 Abbreviations

497 ICC: Intraclass Correlation Coefficient

498 MOE: margin of error

499 NAM: new approach methodologies

500 PG: project group

501 RoB: risk of bias

502 SAG: scientific advisory group

503 SQ: signalling question

504 Definitions

505 **Bias** are systematic errors, or deviations from the truth, in results or inference (Cochrane
506 Collaboration, 2005).

507 **Bias domains** are themes such as e.g. study performance, analysis, and reporting, under
508 which sources of bias/bias items can be organised/grouped.

509 **Bias items** are study properties that may be relevant for introduction of bias in results and/or
510 their interpretation. Criteria are the issues that have to be fulfilled for bias to be avoided. In

511 the guidance document for the INVITES-IN tool there will be criteria for reaching risk-of-bias
512 judgements for each signalling question.

513 **Cell culture studies** refers to cell lines, primary cells, co-cultures, monolayer and 3-D cell
514 systems in the user testing study.

515 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have
516 prevented bias (Cochrane Collaboration, 2005).

517 **Inter-rater reliability** refers to the level of consistency between independent raters when
518 rating the same signalling question for the same study.

519 **In vitro** ("in the glass") tests means that it is done outside of a living organism and it usually
520 involves isolated tissues, organs or cells (ECHA, 2023).

521 **NAMs** have not yet a standard definition. However, there seems to be a general agreement
522 that the term "NAMs" include *in chemico*, *in silico* and *in vitro* studies. One definition is that
523 "NAMs includes any technology, methodology, approach, or combination that can provide
524 information on chemical hazard and risk assessment without the use of animals, including *in*
525 *silico*, *in chemico*, *in vitro*, and *ex vivo* approaches" (ECHA, 2016; EPA, 2018).

526 **Risk of bias** are a measure for systematic errors. Risk of bias tools are used for evaluation
527 of the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have prevented bias
528 (the degree of systematic errors).

529 **Signalling questions** are the questions that the users of the tool answer in order to
530 determine whether the criteria have been fulfilled.

531 **Validity** is the degree to which a result (of a measurement or study) is likely to be true and
532 free of bias (systematic errors) (Cochrane Collaboration, 2005).

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540 [Ethical considerations](#)

541 Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian
542 Institute of Public Health on February 7th, 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is
543 not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.

544 [Declaration of interests](#)

545 Completed declaration of interest forms for each author are available as supplementary
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604

605 **Supplementary materials 1: Identification of cell culture studies** 606 **for the practical exercise**

607 A PubMed search was performed in December 2022 using the population, exposure,
608 outcome (PEO) method. Population (P): *in vitro* studies, restricted to cell culture studies;
609 Exposure (E): chemical substances, tested separately; Outcome (O): negative effects.

610 The search terms used were: ("systematic review") AND (vitro) AND (toxic*), and the search
611 was filtered for within last five years.

612 For a systematic review to be used to collect cell culture studies for the practical exercise,
613 the following eligibility criteria must be fulfilled:

- 614 • A literature search has been performed to identify relevant studies for inclusion
- 615 • It has a clear PECO/PEO statement
- 616 • Quality/ RoB of the included studies has been assessed
- 617 • At least one of the included cell culture studies is categorised as high quality/ low RoB
618 and at least one is categorised as low quality/ high RoB.

619 Two of the authors (G.H.M and G.V.) independently performed the study selection and
620 screened titles and abstracts prior to assessing full-text articles.

621 An overview of the study selection is given in Figure S1.

622

623 **Figure S1.** Flowchart for the selection of systematic reviews for the creation of the literature
624 pools used for the user testing (modified from Moher et al. (2010)).

625 Six systematic reviews were included. These reviews were considered to provide sufficient
626 diversity of cell types used for the experiments and outcomes addressed.

627 Tables S1, S2 and S3 are excel files. An overview of the included systematic reviews is
628 given in Table S1, an overview of the excluded studies, with reason, is given in Table S2,
629 and an overview of the publications collected from the eligible systematic reviews is given in
630 Table S3. Only publications categorised as low quality/ high RoB or high quality/ low RoB
631 are collected. As it is important that cell culture studies having different degrees of RoB for
632 different sources of bias are included in the user testing, we will ensure that the pool of
633 studies for the practical exercise include more than one rating options for each signalling
634 question (see Section 2.1.3). Because we aim to test if the INVITES-IN tool separate
635 studies of lower internal validity from studies of higher internal validity, we select the high
636 and the low categories for use in the test. When four quality/ RoB categories are given,
637 publications in categories one and four are collected whereas publications in categories two
638 or three are not. When three categories are given, publications in categories one and three
639 are collected whereas publications in category two are not.

640 Each collected publication will be tagged with the question (PECO/PEO) of the mother
641 review in which it was found. Cell culture studies from these publications will be selected for
642 the practical exercise as described in Section 2.1.3. The PECO/PEO question will be
643 presented together with the study in the practical exercise.

644 **Supplementary materials 2: The user testing survey**

645 **Part 1**

646 Fill in

647 **I hereby agree to participate in this study**

648 [answer]

649 **Name**

650 [answer]

651 Rate your agreement with the following statements

652 **I found the tool intuitive to use**

653 1. Strongly disagree | 2. Somewhat disagree | 3. Neither agree nor disagree | 4. Somewhat
654 agree | 5. Strongly agree

655 [provide option to give more details]

656 **The tool became easier to apply as I gained more experience in using it**

657 1. Strongly disagree | 2. Somewhat disagree | 3. Neither agree nor disagree | 4. Somewhat
658 agree | 5. Strongly agree

659 [provide option to give more details]

660 **The tool was equally easy to apply to all the studies I evaluated**

661 1. Strongly disagree | 2. Somewhat disagree | 3. Neither agree nor disagree | 4. Somewhat
662 agree | 5. Strongly agree

663 [provide option to give more details]

664 **It was easy to come to consensus with the other reviewer about the rating of the**
665 **studies**

666 1. Strongly disagree | 2. Somewhat disagree | 3. Neither agree nor disagree | 4. Somewhat
667 agree | 5. Strongly agree

668 [provide option to give more details]

669 **The guidance was helpful for understanding how to apply the tool**

670 1. Strongly disagree | 2. Somewhat disagree | 3. Neither agree nor disagree | 4. Somewhat
671 agree | 5. Strongly agree

672 [provide option to give more details]

673 **Part 2**

674 Fill in and select the correct option (this will be requested for each cell culture study rated by
675 the participant).

676 **The time you used to rate cell culture study number 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5** (all time spent on
677 the evaluation, which includes reading the study, identifying the necessary information,
678 conducting additional information gathering (when necessary) and answering and giving
679 reasoning for all the signalling questions): [fill in]

680 **Rate how confident you are that the timing was accurate for cell culture study 1, 2, 3,
681 4 and 5:**

682 1. Very confident | 2. Somewhat confident | 3. Somewhat unsure | 4. Very unsure

683 **Part 3**

684 Answer the following questions

685 **How could the usability of the tool be improved?**

686 [answer]

687 **How could the guidance be improved, as a document to help you use the tool?**

688 [answer]

689 **Which signalling questions did you find most challenging to answer, and why?**

690 [answer]

691 **In what ways did the design of a study affect your ability to assess it with the tool?**

692 [answer]

693 **In what ways did the reporting of a study affect your ability to assess it with the tool?**

694 [answer]

695 **Do you consider some bias to be more impactful than others for the cell culture**
696 **studies you assessed?**

697 [answer]

698 **Do you have any other thoughts or comments about the tool?**

699 [answer]

700 **Supplementary materials 3: Questionnaire for collection of** 701 **participant information**

702 The participant characteristics to be reported and the questions to be answered are
703 presented below.

704 **To be filled in**

705 **I hereby agree to participate in this study**

706 [answer]

707 **Name**

708 [answer]

709 **Country of origin**

710 [answer]

711 **Gender**

712 [answer]

713 **Primary place of employment**

714 [answer]

715 **Secondary place of employment**

716 [answer]

717 **Primary field of expertise**

718 [answer]

719 **Other fields of expertise**

720 [answer]

721 Do you have any financial interests (e.g. employment, shares, grants, or other
722 income) that could be affected by the findings of this study?

723 [If no, answer "None". If yes, please describe the financial interests]

724 Do you have any non-financial interests (e.g. publicly held positions, strong beliefs,
725 or roles in which you are a formal representative of another organisation), that could
726 be affected by the findings of this study?

727 [If no, answer "None". If yes, please describe the non-financial interests]

728 [Select the correct option](#)

729 **How many years of experience do you have with *in vitro* studies?**

730 1. No experience | 2. One to three years | 3. Four to six years | 4. More than six years

731 **How experienced are you with systematic reviews?**

732 1. No experience | 2. Some experience (e.g. been involved in one systematic review or peer-
733 reviewed several systematic reviews) | 3. Moderate experience (conducted study appraisal
734 in at least one systematic review) | 4. Extensive experience (have designed the methods,
735 including selection, modification, or developed study assessment methods, for at least one
736 systematic review)

737 **How many years of experience do you have with chemical risk assessment?**

738 1. No experience | 2. One to three years | 3. Three to six years | 4. More than six years

739